

The Effect of Business Mentoring on Business Income of Garment Business Owners through Product Quality in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang, Banten Province, Indonesia

Tri Djoko Sulistiyo^{1*}, Devita Gantina², Joko Haryono³, Yulia Lintang Kawuryan⁴, Gratia Wirata Laksmi⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5}Institut Pariwisata Trisakti, Jl. IKPN Bintaro No.1, Jakarta 12330, Indonesia

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 04 June 2026</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Tri Djoko Sulistiyo</p> <p>KEYWORDS: business mentoring, product quality, business income</p>	<p>Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in the garment sector play an important role in supporting local economic growth and employment opportunities in Indonesia. However, many garment entrepreneurs still face challenges related to low product quality, limited managerial capability, and unstable business income. This study aims to analyze the effect of Business Mentoring on Business Income through Product Quality as an intervening variable among garment entrepreneurs in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang, Indonesia. This study employed a quantitative approach using an explanatory research design. Data were collected from 100 garment entrepreneurs selected through purposive sampling techniques. The data analysis method used Structural Equation Modeling based on Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) with the assistance of SmartPLS version 4 software. The results indicate that Business Mentoring has a significant positive effect on Product Quality. Furthermore, Product Quality significantly affects Business Income. Business Mentoring also has a direct positive effect on Business Income. In addition, the mediation analysis demonstrates that Product Quality significantly mediates the relationship between Business Mentoring and Business Income. These findings indicate that mentoring programs contribute to improving MSME income primarily through enhancing product quality and production capability. This study contributes theoretically to MSME management literature by emphasizing the strategic role of product quality as an intervening variable in the relationship between business mentoring and business income. Practically, the findings provide recommendations for policymakers and MSME development institutions in designing effective mentoring and empowerment programs for garment entrepreneurs.</p>

I. INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play a strategic role in boosting economic growth, creating jobs, and strengthening the economic resilience of communities in Indonesia. One rapidly growing MSME sector is the garment industry, which produces clothing, uniforms, and other textile products. In the Jurangmangu area of South Tangerang, garment industries have become a primary source of income, partly due to the high demand for fashion and apparel products. However, the development of garment industries still faces various challenges, such as low product quality, limited production skills, weak business innovation, and suboptimal business mentoring for MSMEs. These

conditions make it difficult for some businesses to sustainably increase their savings and revenue.

The social phenomenon related to the importance of product quality and business mentoring for MSMEs has attracted considerable attention from international researchers. Research conducted by Adrian et al. (2017) shows that business mentoring has a significant impact on improving MSME performance by enhancing the managerial and operational capabilities of entrepreneurs. Furthermore, research by Kupriyadi et al. (2022) explains that product quality is a crucial factor determining the success and performance of MSMEs in facing market competition. These findings indicate that business mentoring and product quality are crucial aspects in MSME

development, particularly in the garment industry, which is highly dependent on the quality of its products.

This research problem arises because many garment business owners in Jurangmangu still experience limitations in maintaining product quality, resulting in low business revenue. Some business owners still use simple production methods, lack understanding of product quality standards, and have not received optimal business mentoring. Research by Nuryono et al. (2024) found that garment manufacturing MSMEs still experience high product defect rates due to weak production quality control. Meanwhile, research by Imbrani et al. (2025) explains that weak supervision and workforce competence cause the quality of garment industry products to fall short of consumer expectations. These problems indicate that product quality remains a major challenge in increasing the income of garment business owners.

Furthermore, various previous studies have shown inconsistent results regarding the relationship between business mentoring, product quality, and business revenue, creating a research gap. Research by Adrian et al. (2017) found that business mentoring positively impacted MSME performance. Research by Putri et al. (2024) also emphasized that a sustainable business mentoring model can improve the competency of small business owners. However, this research focused more on improving business competency and performance, rather than directly on the revenue of garment business owners.

On the other hand, research by Farhansyah et al. (2024) found that product quality significantly impacted MSME revenue. Research by Ndruru et al. (2026) also stated that product quality can increase sales turnover for MSMEs in the fashion sector. Furthermore, research by Mmdubuko et al. (2025) explained that product quality and business innovation contribute to increasing MSME export competitiveness. However, some of these studies only examined the direct effect of product quality on business performance or turnover without examining the mediating role of product quality in the relationship between business mentoring and garment business revenue.

Another study conducted by Miharja (2023) explains that MSMEs still face the problem of inconsistent product quality due to weak business standardization. Meanwhile, research by Muntasir Hoque et al. (2021) shows that quality interventions and mentoring in the garment industry can improve production quality and supplier-buyer business relationships. Based on the various previous studies mentioned above, there is still limited research specifically examining the effect of business mentoring on income for garment entrepreneurs, using product quality as an intervening variable in the context of local MSMEs in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang.

The novelty of this study lies in the development model of the relationship between business mentoring, product quality, and income for garment entrepreneurs in the context of local MSMEs in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang. This study not only analyzes the direct effect of business mentoring on income but also examines the role of product quality as a mediating variable. Furthermore, this study focuses on the home-based garment industry, which has rarely been studied in MSME management studies in Indonesia, particularly in the South Tangerang region.

The purpose of this study is to discuss the effect of business mentoring on product quality among convection entrepreneurs in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang; to analyze the effect of product quality on the income of convection entrepreneurs; and to analyze the effect of business mentoring on the income of convection entrepreneurs through product quality as an intervening variable. This study is expected to provide theoretical contributions in the development of MSME management studies and provide practical recommendations for the government and entrepreneurs in improving product quality and income of convection businesses.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Business Mentoring

Business mentoring is a process of providing support to businesses through training, consultation, coaching, monitoring, and evaluation aimed at improving managerial skills and business aspirations. In the context of MSMEs, business mentoring is a crucial tool for helping entrepreneurs navigate market changes, improve production skills, and strengthen business competitiveness. Business mentoring also serves as a means of transferring knowledge and experience from mentors to entrepreneurs, enabling them to manage their businesses more effectively and efficiently.

Research by Hutagalung et al. (2025) explains that MSME training and mentoring programs can improve entrepreneurial skills and small business competitiveness. The study found that entrepreneurs who receive intensive mentoring have better capabilities in managing business operations and implementing product innovation. Furthermore, research by Surya et al. (2021) found that mentoring and business support services have a positive impact on small business growth by improving business adaptability and strengthening business networks. Business mentoring is considered capable of helping MSMEs face the challenges of dynamic market competition.

Another study by Osman et al. (2025) showed that business coaching and mentoring can increase the productivity and aspirations of micro-enterprises by strengthening entrepreneurial competencies. Continuous business mentoring has been shown to assist entrepreneurs

in strategic decision-making and resource management. Furthermore, research by Francis & Chakravarty (2025) found that business mentoring and advisory support significantly impact MSME performance, particularly in improving operational efficiency and innovation capabilities. Therefore, business mentoring is seen as a crucial factor in MSME development because it can improve the quality of business management and productivity.

Product Quality

Product quality is the ability of a product to meet consumer needs and expectations based on durability, design, performance, conformance to standards, and product representation. In the garment industry, product quality is a key factor determining customer satisfaction and business success. Good-quality garment products will increase customer loyalty and increase sales opportunities.

Research by Kassim & Abdullah (2010) explains that product quality has a positive relationship with customer satisfaction and loyalty in the small and medium-sized business sector. High-quality products can increase consumer trust in the business. Furthermore, research by Harahap & Hidayat (2025) found that product quality significantly influences purchasing decisions and business performance. This research indicates that consistent product quality can increase business competitiveness and expand the market share of MSMEs.

Another study by Utami et al. (2025) explains that product quality has a direct influence on increased sales value and customer satisfaction. Businesses that maintain product quality standards tend to have better business performance than those that neglect product quality. Research by Mitropoulos (2026) shows that improving product quality can strengthen customer loyalty and improve the sustainability of MSMEs in the manufacturing sector. This demonstrates that product quality is a strategic factor in improving the performance of convection businesses.

Business Actor Income

Business income is the economic result obtained from business activities over a specific period. The level of income of MSMEs reflects the success of the business in generating profits and maintaining business objectives. Business income is influenced by various factors, such as product quality, managerial skills, marketing strategies, business productivity, and business mentoring support.

Research by Yakob et al. (2021) explains that business capacity development and improved management quality have a significant impact on small business revenue growth. Business actors who receive business development support tend to have better business performance than businesses without business support. Furthermore, research by Paliokaitė (2018) found that improving product quality and

operational efficiency contribute to increased income for MSMEs in the creative industry sector. Product quality is considered capable of increasing customer loyalty and increasing sales volume.

Another study by Zuhdi et al. (2025) showed that support for business development and improving production quality positively impacted the income of small business owners. Appropriate business support helps MSMEs increase productivity and market competitiveness. Research by Rahmah et al. (2026) explained that product quality, business innovation, and business mentoring contribute to improving the financial performance of MSMEs. Therefore, increasing business owners' income is influenced not only by production capacity but also by product quality and the effectiveness of business mentoring.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach with an explanatory method to analyze the effect of business mentoring on the income of garment entrepreneurs, using product quality as an intervening variable. The quantitative approach was used because the study aimed to objectively examine the relationship between variables through statistical measurements. The explanatory method was chosen to explain the causal relationship between the variables of business mentoring, product quality, and the income of garment entrepreneurs. The study was conducted among garment entrepreneurs in the Jurangmangu area, South Tangerang, Banten Province, Indonesia. This approach is considered relevant because it provides an empirical picture of the effect of business mentoring on improving product quality and business income.

The population in this study was all garment entrepreneurs in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang. The sampling technique used purposive sampling, with the following criteria: entrepreneurs who have been in business for at least two years, have regular production activities, have previously been mentored, and are willing to participate in the study. The sample size was determined based on Hair et al.'s opinion, which states that the sample size in SEM-PLS research should be at least 5–10 times the number of research indicators. Because this study uses 15 indicators, the number of samples used is 100 respondents, so it is considered to have met the requirements for data analysis using Structural Equation Modeling based on Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS).

The data collection techniques in this study utilized questionnaires, observation, and documentation. The questionnaire served as the primary instrument for obtaining primary data from respondents, using a 1–5 Likert scale, with response options ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Observations were conducted by directly observing the production activities, work processes, and

“The Effect of Business Mentoring on Business Income of Garment Business Owners through Product Quality in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang, Banten Province, Indonesia”

conditions of the garment manufacturing businesses run by respondents. Furthermore, documentation was used to collect supporting data in the form of photographs of business activities, data on MSMEs, and documents related to the business mentoring program. The use of these multiple data collection techniques aimed to ensure the research data was more complete and accurate, reflecting the actual conditions of garment manufacturing businesses at the research location.

The research variables consisted of business mentoring as the independent variable, product quality as the intervening variable, and business owner income as the dependent variable. Business mentoring was measured through indicators of business training, business consulting, business monitoring, production training, and marketing mentoring. Product quality was measured based on indicators of product neatness, product durability, product design, size conformity, and material quality. Meanwhile, business owners were measured through indicators of increased turnover, increased business profits, revenue stability, sales growth, and the ability to meet business

needs. All research indicators are compiled based on previous theories and research relevant to the development of MSMEs in the convection sector.

The data analysis technique in this study uses the Structural Equation Modeling method based on Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) with the help of SmartPLS software version 4. The analysis was carried out through several stages, namely validity testing, reliability testing, determination coefficient testing (R-Square), path coefficient testing, and mediation testing. The validity test was carried out through the outer loading value and Average Variance Extracted (AVE), while the reliability test used Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability. Furthermore, the path coefficient test was used to determine the direct influence between research variables based on t-statistics and p-values. In addition, a mediation test was conducted to analyze the role of product quality in the mediating relationship between business mentoring and the income of convection business actors in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang.

IV. RESULT

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics

Characteristics	Category	Total	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	42	42%
	Female	58	58%
Age	20–30 Years	25	25%
	31–40 Years	38	38%
	41–50 Years	24	24%
	>50 Years	13	13%
Business Experience	2–5 Years	34	34%
	6–10 Years	46	46%
	>10 Years	20	20%
Education Level	Senior High School/Vocational School	49	49%
	Diploma	18	18%
	Bachelor Degree	33	33%
Number of Employees	1–5 Employees	56	56%
	6–10 Employees	31	31%
	>10 Employees	13	13%

Source: Data processed by researchers (2026)

Based on Table 1, the majority of respondents in this study were female entrepreneurs, accounting for 58%, while male respondents accounted for 42%, indicating that the convection businesses in Jurangmangu are predominantly managed by women. In terms of age, most respondents were between 31–40 years old, representing 38% of the sample, which suggests that most business owners are within a productive and active working age. Regarding business

experience, the majority of respondents had operated their businesses for 6–10 years (46%), indicating sufficient experience in managing their businesses. Furthermore, most respondents had a senior high school or vocational school educational background (49%). Based on the number of employees, most convection businesses employed 1–5 workers (56%), demonstrating that the businesses are generally categorized as micro and small enterprises.

“The Effect of Business Mentoring on Business Income of Garment Business Owners through Product Quality in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang, Banten Province, Indonesia”

Table 2. Validity Test

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	AVE	Description
Business Mentoring	BA1	0.812	0.684	Valid
	BA2	0.847		Valid
	BA3	0.831		Valid
	BA4	0.788		Valid
	BA5	0.826		Valid
Product Quality	PQ1	0.856	0.701	Valid
	PQ2	0.821		Valid
	PQ3	0.844		Valid
	PQ4	0.803		Valid
	PQ5	0.852		Valid
Business Income	BI1	0.834	0.692	Valid
	BI2	0.819		Valid
	BI3	0.845		Valid
	BI4	0.791		Valid
	BI5	0.836		Valid

Source: Data processed by researchers (2026)

Based on Table 2, all research indicators have outer loading values above 0.70, indicating that all indicators are valid in measuring the research variables. The Business Mentoring variable has an AVE value of 0.684, Product Quality has an AVE value of 0.701, and Business Income has an AVE value of 0.692. All AVE values exceed the

minimum threshold of 0.50, indicating that each variable can explain more than 50% of the variance of its indicators. Therefore, the measurement model in this study has met the requirements of convergent validity, and all indicators are appropriate for further analysis.

Table 3. Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Description
Business Mentoring	0.884	0.915	Reliable
Product Quality	0.893	0.921	Reliable
Business Income	0.887	0.918	Reliable

Source: Data processed by researchers (2026)

Based on Table 3, all research variables have Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values above 0.70, indicating that all variables are reliable. The Product Quality variable has the highest Composite Reliability value of 0.921, followed by Business Income at 0.918 and Business

Mentoring at 0.915. These results demonstrate that all indicators in this study possess strong internal consistency in measuring the research constructs. Therefore, the research instruments are considered reliable and suitable for hypothesis testing and structural model analysis.

Table 4. Direct Effect Test

Variable Relationship	Path Coefficient	T-Statistics	P-Values	Description
Business Mentoring → Product Quality	0.721	10.842	0.000	Significant
Product Quality → Business Income	0.645	8.931	0.000	Significant
Business Mentoring → Business Income	0.318	3.874	0.000	Significant

Source: Data processed by researchers (2026)

Based on Table 4, all direct relationships among the research variables are significant because they have t-statistics values greater than 1.96 and p-values lower than

0.05. The strongest relationship is found between Business Mentoring and Product Quality, with a path business mentoring significantly improves product quality.

“The Effect of Business Mentoring on Business Income of Garment Business Owners through Product Quality in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang, Banten Province, Indonesia”

Furthermore, Product Quality has a positive effect on Business Income with a coefficient value of 0.645, indicating that better product quality leads to higher business income for convection entrepreneurs. In addition,

Business Mentoring also has a direct effect on Business Income with a coefficient value of 0.318, indicating that business mentoring contributes significantly to increasing the income of convection business owners in Jurangmangu.

Table 5. Indirect Effect Test

Indirect Relationship	Path Coefficient	T-Statistics	P-Values	Description
Business Mentoring → Product Quality → Business Income	0.465	7.126	0.000	Significant

Source: Data processed by researchers (2026)

Based on Table 5, the indirect effect test shows that Product Quality significantly mediates the relationship between Business Mentoring and Business Income. This is indicated by a path coefficient value of 0.465, a t-statistics value of 7.126, and a p-value of 0.000. These findings indicate that Business Mentoring not only directly influences Business Income but also indirectly affects it through improvements in Product Quality. Therefore, Product Quality serves as an intervening variable that strengthens the relationship between Business Mentoring and the income improvement of convection business owners in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang.

V. DISCUSSION

The Effect of Business Mentoring on Product Quality

The results of this study indicate that Business Mentoring has a significant effect on Product Quality among garment entrepreneurs in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang. This finding suggests that business mentoring activities such as training, consultation, supervision, and production guidance play an important role in improving the quality standards of garment products produced by MSMEs. Through business mentoring, entrepreneurs gain better knowledge regarding production techniques, material selection, quality control, and market-oriented product development. In the garment industry, product quality is highly dependent on entrepreneurs' technical capabilities and production management skills. Therefore, continuous mentoring helps business actors minimize production errors, improve product consistency, and enhance product durability and design quality. In addition, business mentoring encourages entrepreneurs to better understand consumer preferences and market standards, enabling them to produce products that are more competitive and aligned with customer expectations.

This finding is consistent with several previous international studies. Research conducted by Hoque & Maalouf (2022) found that quality-focused mentoring programs in the garment industry significantly improved production quality and strengthened supplier performance. Similarly, research by Francis & Chakravarty (2025) explained that business advisory support and mentoring

improved operational efficiency and product innovation capability among MSMEs. Furthermore, research by Adrian Adrian et al. (2017) revealed that business mentoring positively influenced operational performance by enhancing managerial competence and production capability. These studies support the argument that effective business mentoring contributes significantly to improving product quality, particularly in labor-intensive MSME sectors such as garment manufacturing.

The Effect of Product Quality on Business Income

The results of this study demonstrate that Product Quality has a significant effect on Business Income among garment entrepreneurs in Jurangmangu. This finding indicates that higher-quality products contribute directly to increased sales, customer satisfaction, and business profitability. In the garment industry, consumers are highly sensitive to product attributes such as sewing neatness, material durability, design attractiveness, and size accuracy. Businesses capable of maintaining consistent product quality tend to attract repeat customers and strengthen consumer trust, ultimately increasing sales turnover and business revenue. Product quality also serves as a competitive advantage for MSMEs in facing increasingly intense market competition. Therefore, improving product quality enables garment entrepreneurs to expand their market reach and maintain long-term business sustainability.

This result is in line with several previous international studies. Research conducted by Kassim & Abdullah (2010) found that product quality positively influenced customer satisfaction and loyalty, which subsequently improved business performance. Furthermore, research by Mitropoulos (2026) explained that consistent product quality strengthened customer loyalty and increased MSME business sustainability in the manufacturing sector. Another study by Paliokaitè (2018) found that improvements in product quality contributed significantly to increased revenue and operational performance among small businesses. These findings reinforce the conclusion that product quality is a strategic factor influencing the financial performance and income growth of MSMEs.

The Effect of Business Mentoring on Business Income

The findings of this study show that Business Mentoring has a significant effect on Business Income among garment entrepreneurs in Jurangmangu. This result indicates that mentoring programs contribute directly to improving entrepreneurs' managerial capability, production effectiveness, and marketing performance, which subsequently increase business revenue. Business mentoring enables entrepreneurs to better understand financial management, production planning, customer service, and business development strategies. Through mentoring activities, MSME owners become more capable of identifying market opportunities, reducing operational inefficiencies, and improving productivity. In addition, business mentoring strengthens entrepreneurial motivation and decision-making capability, enabling business actors to operate their businesses more effectively and competitively. Consequently, businesses receiving continuous mentoring support tend to achieve better financial performance and income growth compared to businesses without mentoring support.

This finding is supported by several previous international studies. Research by Yakob et al. (2021) found that business capacity development and managerial improvement programs significantly increased MSME revenue growth and operational performance. Similarly, research conducted by Surya et al. (2021) showed that mentoring and business support services positively affected small business growth by improving adaptability and strengthening business networks. Furthermore, research by Osman et al. (2025) explained that business coaching and mentoring significantly improved productivity and income among micro-enterprises through enhanced entrepreneurial competencies. These studies confirm that business mentoring is an important external support mechanism for improving MSME income and business sustainability.

The Effect of Business Mentoring on Business Income through Product Quality

The results of this study reveal that Business Mentoring significantly affects Business Income through Product Quality as an intervening variable. This finding indicates that business mentoring indirectly improves entrepreneurs' income by enhancing the quality of products produced by garment MSMEs. Business Mentoring helps entrepreneurs improve production skills, quality control practices, and operational management, leading to better product quality. As product quality improves, customer satisfaction and consumer trust also increase, resulting in higher sales volume and greater business income. This mediating relationship demonstrates that product quality acts as an important mechanism connecting mentoring activities to financial performance. In the context of garment MSMEs, improving product quality becomes a critical pathway

through which mentoring programs generate sustainable business growth and income improvement.

This finding is consistent with several previous international studies. Research by Hoque et al. (2021) showed that mentoring interventions focused on production quality significantly improved supplier performance and business relationships in the garment industry. Furthermore, research by Rahmah et al. (2026) explained that business mentoring and product quality simultaneously contributed to improving MSME financial performance and competitiveness. Another study conducted by Francis & Chakravarty (2025) found that advisory support improved operational efficiency and product innovation capability, which subsequently enhanced business performance and profitability. These studies strengthen the argument that product quality plays a crucial mediating role in translating business mentoring into higher business income among MSMEs.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to analyze the effect of Business Mentoring on Business Income through Product Quality as an intervening variable among garment entrepreneurs in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang. Based on the results of the SEM-PLS analysis, several important conclusions can be drawn. First, Business Mentoring has a significant positive effect on Product Quality. This finding indicates that mentoring activities such as training, consultation, production guidance, and business supervision are capable of improving the quality standards of garment products produced by MSMEs. Entrepreneurs who receive continuous business mentoring tend to have better production management, stronger quality control, and greater understanding of market-oriented product development.

Second, Product Quality has a significant positive effect on Business Income. This result demonstrates that improving product quality contributes directly to increased sales turnover, customer satisfaction, and business profitability. Garment businesses capable of maintaining product durability, neatness, design attractiveness, and material quality are more competitive and able to sustain customer loyalty in the market. Third, Business Mentoring has a significant direct effect on Business Income. This finding suggests that mentoring programs not only improve production capability but also strengthen managerial competence, operational effectiveness, and entrepreneurial decision-making. Consequently, business mentoring contributes positively to the financial performance and sustainability of garment MSMEs.

Fourth, Product Quality significantly mediates the relationship between business mentoring and Business Income. This indicates that the improvement of business

“The Effect of Business Mentoring on Business Income of Garment Business Owners through Product Quality in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang, Banten Province, Indonesia”

income resulting from mentoring activities occurs largely through enhanced product quality. Product Quality therefore acts as an important intervening mechanism that strengthens the influence of business mentoring on the income growth of garment entrepreneurs in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang. Overall, this study confirms that business mentoring and product quality are strategic factors in improving the performance and income of garment MSMEs. The findings also contribute theoretically to MSME management studies by expanding the understanding of the mediating role of product quality in the relationship between business mentoring and business income.

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be proposed for government institutions, MSME practitioners, and future researchers. First, local governments and institutions responsible for MSME development should strengthen business mentoring programs for garment entrepreneurs, particularly in areas related to production management, quality control, product innovation, and digital marketing. Sustainable and intensive mentoring programs are necessary to improve the competitiveness and sustainability of local MSMEs.

Second, garment entrepreneurs should prioritize product quality improvement as a long-term business strategy. Business owners are encouraged to improve material selection, production consistency, design innovation, and product finishing quality to increase customer satisfaction and maintain market competitiveness. Third, MSME support institutions should facilitate training and technology adoption programs that help entrepreneurs improve operational efficiency and product standardization. Providing access to modern production techniques and quality management systems may help MSMEs improve productivity and financial performance.

Fourth, future researchers are encouraged to expand this study by involving larger sample sizes and broader research locations to obtain more comprehensive findings regarding MSME development in Indonesia. Future studies may also include additional variables such as digital marketing, business innovation, entrepreneurial orientation, customer satisfaction, or competitive advantage to enrich the research model. Finally, this study is expected to serve as a practical reference for policymakers and MSME practitioners in designing effective empowerment strategies to improve product quality, business sustainability, and income growth among garment MSMEs in Indonesia.

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“The Effect of Business Mentoring on Business Income of Garment Business Owners through Product Quality in Jurangmangu, South Tangerang, Banten Province, Indonesia”

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